

D4.2 Report from the workshops with recommendations for EURAXESS

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Author(s)	Xavier Eekhout Chicharro and Izaskun Lacunza
Other Contributors	
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Information in this report that may influence other GEARING-Roles tasks

Linked Task	Points of Relevance
T4.1	Task 4.1 Promotion and evolution of the Open, transparent, merit-based recruitment toolkit (OTM-r toolkit) towards a gender-equality friendly OTM-r toolkit

T4.2

Task 4.2 Training on how to develop researcher career development plans in research performing organizations

GEARING-Roles project

GEARING-Roles is a four-year (January 2019 – December 2022) Coordination and Support Action project that will bring together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project therefore has a firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers and working towards real institutional change. This multidisciplinary, multinational, and multi-sectorial collaboration will be supported by training in this space, mentoring activities, awareness raising campaigns as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

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List of Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
ERA	European Research Area
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
HRS4R	Human Resources Strategy for Researchers
OTM-R	Open, transparent, merit-based recruitment
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This report compiles key recommendations on how to better integrate the gender dimension in the EURAXESS network. The recommendations were gathered through different workshops (i) Training workshop: Building a gender equality plan – the role of participative methods, ii) Webinar Good Practices for Achieving Gender Equality in Recruitment and Career Development Of Researchers In Europe, and iii) GEARING Roles OTM-R Training Workshop), and through the input gathered by both mentors and mentees of the [Feminist Leadership in Science \(FELISE\)](#) mentoring programmed organized within work package 4 (WP4).

1. The European Research Area (ERA)

The European Research Area (ERA) was launched in 2000 with the ambition to create a single, borderless market for research, innovation and technology across the EU. Thus, its aim is to achieve the free circulation of researchers and knowledge enabling:

- More effective national research systems
- Trans-national co-operation and competition
- Gender equality
- Optimal circulation, access to and transfer of scientific knowledge
- Open labour market for researchers

In order to achieve an open labour market for researchers, a different number of initiatives have been put in place by the European Commission (EC) in close collaboration with Member States and research funding and performing organizations throughout the European Union and beyond.

1.1 The EURAXESS initiative

The EURAXESS initiative is delivering information and support services to professional researchers. Backed by the European Union, member states and associated countries, it supports researcher mobility and career development, while enhancing scientific collaboration between Europe and the world. The network, composed by national coordinators (so called Bridgehead Organizations) and regional nodes works together in delivering this services and supporting mobility along Europe and beyond. Members of the network are diverse (they can be sitting on European projects offices, human resources departments, etc. in their institutions), hold much different expertise and are working together for over a decade.

The [EURAXESS Europe website](#) and the EURAXESS national portals offer vast information relevant for mobile researchers (work permits, visas, schooling of children, etc.) and job and funding opportunities. Moreover, since 2014, the network is focusing strongly in developing resources and services to support researchers in their career development. A number of initiatives and EURAXESS related EU projects have focused in creating content and delivering training for researchers so they can develop and fulfil their career expectations. As a result of this work, the EURAXESS Europe website offers a devoted section to career development in which researchers and institutions can find resources to boost their careers and develop career development services, respectively.

As it is well known, both EURAXESS priorities (international mobility and career development) are two strongly gendered researchers' careers dimensions. Aware of it, a number of EURAXESS initiatives and EURAXESS related EU projects work packages and tasks have reflected on the gender dimensions of their services.

However, this approach is not systematically included in all EURAXESS services for researchers. One of the objectives of GEARING Roles WP4 is to look into the EURAXESS services with a gender perspective and to issue recommendations on how to achieve EURAXESS also actively fostering gender equality.

1.2 The Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers and the Human Resources Excellence in Research Award

A crucial policy document for the roll out of an open labour market for researchers in Europe was the one published by the EC in 2005, the [Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers](#) (Charter & Code hereinafter). This document is composed of 40 principles detailing the rights and obligations of researchers, as well as the rights and obligations of organizations recruiting researchers. Since its publication, the Charter & Code has become a widely accepted framework for human resources departments in research organisations, with [more than 1200 organisations](#) across Europe having endorsed it publicly.

In an effort to roll out the Charter & Code, throughout Europe, the EC launched the '[HR Excellence in Research Award](#)' which recognises institutions making progress in aligning their human resources policies to the 40 principles of the Charter & Code, based on a customized action plan/HR strategy. This aligning process is called *Human Resources Strategy for Researchers* (HRS4R), and to date, [almost 600 organizations](#) across Europe have implemented it and received the award.

One of the key aims of the Charter and Code, and the HRS4R as the implementation mechanism of its principles, is to contribute to the development of a common open, transparent, merit based recruitment (OTM-R) for researchers in Europe. OTM-R ensures that the best person for the job is recruited, guarantees equal opportunities and access for all, facilitates developing an international portfolio (cooperation, competition, mobility) and makes research careers more attractive.

This way, the Charter and Code provides the framework for implementing the mandate of EURAXESS in supporting researchers in their mobility and career development. As a matter of fact, many of the actions which can be implemented as part of the institutional HRS4R actions plans tend to be directly related to the EURAXESS activities in the institution (e.g., publishing in EURAXESS Jobs to meet the transparency requirements of the OTM-r, career development support for researchers or instruments to support researcher mobility).

Currently, the Charter and Code already includes a gender balance principle and a few more mentions to gender equality throughout the rest of the principles, but after more than 15 years it is quite clear that the document falls short on addressing gender equality in research in a systematic way.

As the different actions within WP4 of GEARING Roles have followed the principles of "EURAXESS activities supporting the implementation of institutional gender equality plans", the setting has provided the opportunity to gather input and lessons to strengthen the gender dimension of EURAXESS support activities in particular, and to the Charter & Code as the policy framework of the EURAXESS initiative.

2. GEARING roles workshops and the “Feminist Leadership in Science-FELISE” mentoring programme as input to gather recommendations

GEARING Roles has been a good opportunity to bring in together the EURAXESS and the gender equality in research and innovation communities to discuss how to better integrate two key ERA priorities: an open labour for researchers and gender equality in research and innovation. Next, an overview of EURAXESS activities implemented as part of WP4 of GEARING Roles is reviewed. These activities had the primary aim of supporting gender equality plan implementers in issues related to women career progression, although a secondary aim was precisely to use this experience to gather input for drafting the recommendations included in section 3 of this report.

Training workshop: Building a gender equality plan – the role of participative methods (Oxford, June 20-21 2019)

This was one of the several trainings provided by Yellow Window to support Gender Equality Plan (GEP) implementers of the GEARING Roles project. More specifically, the training addressed participative methods which will help the institutions along the process of designing and implementing their GEPs.

One of these exercises was the Lotus Blossom which allows participants to brainstorm around a certain problem providing ideas in tow waves (first level ideas are copied into the second level, to generate new ideas, and so on). The exercise, which was primarily aimed at getting familiarized with the methodology, addressed the problem *How to avoid gender bias during a face-to-face interview?*, turned out to be extremely useful for compiling recommendations from GEP implementing partners on how to address recruiting processes in order avoid gender biases, a content which also contributed to the updated the OTM-R Checklist (D4.1).

Picture 1. OBU training on participative methods

Webinar: Good Practices for Achieving Gender Equality in Recruitment and Career Development Of Researchers In Europe (June 26 2019)

This webinar took place on June 27th 2019 focusing on sharing good practices in supporting researcher careers for achieving gender equality. The webinar included presentations from the University of Zurich, University of Vigo and the Norwegian University of Science and Technology, which shared their institutional practices in support of gender equality related with job advertisement, recruitment, promotion and career development

As an overarching theme across all presentations were the connections between the ERA priorities Open Labour Market for Researchers and Gender Equality, particularly focused around the Charter & Code and its implementation through the HRS4R.

The good practices presented and the audience composition provided a perfect arena to consult on possible actions to foster gender equality in the advertising and application phase, the selection and evaluation phase, the appointment and/or through career development support.

Picture 2. Screenshot from the webinar: Good practices for Achieving Gender Equality in Recruitment & Career Development

GEARING Roles OTM-R Training Workshop (Lisbon, November 28 2019)

The 1st Consortium Meeting of GEARING-Roles organised in Lisbon after the 1st GEARING-Roles Conference provided the possibility to organize a training for the GEARING Roles partners addressing in detail the connections between the Charter & Code and the OTM-r checklist to guide a structured discussion of how the checklist's gender dimension could be further reinforced. Although this workshop was specifically targeted at the preparation of D4.1, the information collected also touched on potential EURAXESS actions.

Feminist Leadership in Science-FELISE mentoring programme (June 2020-February 2021)

35 pairs of junior researchers and senior researchers coming from the Gearing roles implementing institutions participated in the FELISE mentoring programme (see D 4.3 and D 4.4 for further details on the programme) and have actively participated in this 9 months mentoring programme. During the course of the programme, a kick off and final survey have been issued and 3 keynote online presentation offered, which has allowed to discuss with participants about their views and recommendations and the programme and the content offered (handbook, EURAXESS resources, etc.). This informal input has also been used as a source of information to compile recommendations for EURAXESS.

Picture 3. OTM-R Training Workshop Lisbon

Workshop on Career Development in the framework of the FELISE Mentoring Programme (October 28 2020)

As part of the FELISE mentoring programme, it is worth highlighting the training focused on professional development planning for researchers, in which mentees were introduced to tools to manage their own professional development by practising a skills prioritisation and gaining practice in how to set objectives, reflect on progress, and provide evidence about professional competencies. It was organized on the 28th of October 2020 in two sessions to facilitate participation and 28 of the 35 mentees participated, and the feedback collected has also contributed to the recommendations below.

Picture 4. Workshop on Career Development in the framework of the FELISE Mentoring Programme

3. Key recommendations on how to better integrate the gender dimension into the ERA open labour market for researchers' initiatives (EURAXESS and the Charter & Code)

This section compiles some recommendations for the EURAXESS initiative and related tools (Charter and Code and the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers) to better integrate a gender perspective and, thus, a better and more tailored services to women researchers.

3.1 For the EURAXESS initiative

➤ To mainstream gender into EURAXESS services

Mobility of researchers and their career development are strongly gendered. The EURAXESS initiative is offering direct support to researchers in very many different aspects such as visas, work permits, dual careers (supporting researcher's spouses to better integrate in a new destiny), cultural integration, etc. Moreover, fostering career development services is also a priority for EURAXESS since 2014. It is recommended that the EURAXESS community issues guidelines to their members on how to mainstream the gender dimension into their services.

From the aggregated point of view, the EURAXESS initiative gathers statistics from the whole community in order to monitor the number of researchers actually approaching the network with queries the areas that are relevant for EURAXESS services (<https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/information>). In 2019, more than 6000 queries from mobile researchers were reported by the EURAXESS network. It is recommended this statistics include sex-disaggregated data as they can be a wealth of information on potential gendered use of the service and can also provide very relevant information on the kind of requests/concerns mobile researchers have depending on their gender.

➤ To devote specific section in the EURAXESS portal to gender equality in research and innovation in Europe with relevant links and resources and review the language in the portals as to make them gender-neutral.

The European Research Area priorities cannot work in silos. This is especially important when it comes to open labour market for researchers and gender equality in research and innovation priorities because of their close connection.

It is recommended to include a devoted section on the EURAXESS European portal (and the EURAXESS national portals) with relevant information regarding gender equality at the EU level and also at the national level. This section may acknowledge the commitment of EURAXESS in fostering gender equality in research and offer their own content and links to external gender equality tools.

Also, it is recommended that the content offered at the EU and National EURAXESS portals is properly reviewed to ensure gender neutrality.

➤ To offer training on gender equality in research and innovation to EURAXESS staff

Because of its size (over 600 institutions all over Europe) and diversity, the EURAXESS initiative is very much focused on offering training to its community as to guarantee an even level of service throughout Europe. It is

common that periodically, a number of trainings are offered to EURAXESS staff with the ultimate aim of enhancing the mobility and career development support services to researchers.

It is recommended that training on gender equality in research and innovation is systematically considered as a cross-cutting topic for the EURAXESS community as to make sure that the services provided to the researchers include a gender perspective.

➤ To develop a stronger cooperation among the EURAXESS and the gender equality services within research institutions

As discussed above, the EURAXESS community is diverse from many points of view: geographically (more than 40 countries belong to the country), institutionally (research performing organizations of all sizes, higher education centres, public and private centres...) and, also important in the framework of this report, in the level of gender equality awareness and commitment.

It is recommended to develop stronger cooperation among the EURAXESS and the gender equality services within research institutions as they can mutually benefit from this cooperation. This cooperation may lead to finding connections on relevant services which foster both gender equality and career development and mobility of researchers (e.g., capacity building actions on leadership, dual career support, etc.).

➤ To develop career support services specifically devoted to women researchers.

Not only should EURAXESS Services be delivered with a gender equality perspective, but with the proper synergies (e.g., coordination with the staff in charge of the designing and implementing GEPs), EURAXESS services could actively contribute to structural change. This is particularly clear in the case of mentoring programmes designed to support women researchers in their careers in order to tackle the leaky pipeline effect, as well as to any other career development support services ultimately supporting women leadership roles in research institutions (e.g., trainings on leadership-related skills, preparing career development plans).

3.2 For the Charter and Code and the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers award

➤ To review the current definition of the “gender balance” Charter and Code Principle

Out of the current 40 principles of the Charter and Code, one addresses “gender balance”. This is the definition (valid since 2005) of the principle: “Employers and/or funders should aim for a representative gender balance at all levels of staff, including at supervisory and managerial level. This should be achieved on the basis of an equal opportunity policy at recruitment and at the subsequent career stages without, however, taking precedence over quality and competence criteria. To ensure equal treatment, selection and evaluation committees should have an adequate gender balance”.

It is recommended to review the current definition of the principle as to incorporate the current trends in gender equality, which go beyond the concept of quantitative gender balance, do not confront quality to gender equality and incorporate integrating gender perspective in research.

➤ To mainstream gender into the Charter and Code and the Human Resources strategy for researchers

Gender equality in research is a complex, multifactor challenge and it needs to be tackled at very many different levels of the research environment. Many of the principles of the Charter and Code have a very clear gender perspective (just to name a few: recruitment, career development, salaries, supervision, evaluation, good practice in research).

On top of the above recommendation, it is recommended to identify those principles in which gender is a fundamental aspect to be addressed and, either specifically highlighting in each of those principles or make the gender balance principle to be a principle that needs to be mainstreamed throughout the whole Charter and Code.

➤ To mainstream gender into the Open, Transparent, Merit-based recruitment toolkit

Further elaborating on the above recommendation, the gender dimension should also be included in the Open, Transparent, Merit-based recruitment toolkit that helps institutions assess their progress towards this goal.

It is recommended to review and enrich the Open, Transparent, Merit-based recruitment toolkit with a gender perspective. It is well known that the more open and transparent the recruitment processes are, the more gender equal the process is. However, this can even be more fostered when a gender perspective is added to the process. Just as an example, good practices on the advertising phase in order to attract women can be applied. In line with this recommendation, GEARING Roles published a proposal of the OTM-r checklist with the gender equality dimension reinforced as part of *D4.1 Recommendations on how to evolve the OTM-r Toolkit under a gender lenses*, which can also be consulted in the [GEARING Roles website](#).

➤ To assure a good coordination among the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers award (HRS4R) and institutional gender equality plans (GEPs)

The Human Resources Strategy for Researchers is a comprehensive approach to human resources in research management. It does not have a prescriptive nature and it aims at inspiring institutions to align their policies towards a European standard. Because of its wide approach to human resources (covering from research freedom to supervision practices and passing through co-authorship, for instance) the level of detail and depth is by definition superficial.

For example, the need to advance on more details about what the European Commission (EC) understood under the principle “recruitment” was the reason for the Open, Transparent, Merit-based recruitment toolkit to be launched. By “adding” this toolkit to the Charter and Code, the EC became more prescriptive on how the recruitment principle, which is a priority, is expected to be rolled out in EU institutions.

In the same fashion, Gender Equality Plans are much more in depth plans for achieving gender equality in research institutions than the Charter and Code. In a way, the Charter and Code is an overarching strategy of institutions while GEPs are in depth plans for addressing gender equality.

It is recommended that, in those institutions in which both the HRS4R and a GEP are in place, they are well coordinated and synergies found.